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- 20190514_OO_student5_CODE.txt
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- 20190517_OO_student6_CODE.txt
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- 20190523_OO_student11_CODE.txt
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- 20190604_OO_student14_CODE.txt

File outline

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1 [00:00:00]
2
3 R: Awesome, perfect... Ok, then I'd like to start with...
4 S: God, that's Java!
5 R: Oh, yeah, [laughs] Ehm, yeah, Java, 'cause you're doing a Java course, so... You prefer Python or...?
6 S: I prefer C++ because that's until now the... but it gets in the end of the year it everytime gets like, ah, now I have
a, I have a big understanding of the language. But only at the end of the year. First you have like, the first twenty, or
the first twelve weeks you have everytime you have snippets, but I don't really get the language how in total works. And
now it comes that Java gets for me also, like, a little bit familiar. Yeah.
7
8 [00:00:58]
9 [BEGIN TASK 34A]
10 R: Yeah, I couldn't. I completely recognize that. Well, I'm glad to have you here then, thank you! All right, well, you
see, the task what I want you to do, that's a question and that's the code that comes with it so you can read it.
11 S: Pfff... So do I tell what I now do?
12 R: Yeah.
13 S: I'm looking at the array because there's an int array in the beginning. I see that it is the main, so it would get
executed in the beginning, so I don't have to call it and stuff like that. And the array contains out of non-special int
values. Ehm, there's still now, there is a fixed size, ehm, and there will get now, you have an "int current", which is a
variable and this gets the value in when values are in the array number zero, so the first one 25, so current gets 25. And
for every, this is enhanced... Ehm... enhanced for-loop. where you go for the whole array with the variable "value" and if
value is smaller than current, so if for all integers array if it is smaller than 25 the current gets this value. So, it
goes through the array every time, or for every new element in the array it compares it to, and then when it gets smaller
it gets the new array. So it searches the smallest value in this array, so "find_min" would I say is the, yeah.
14 R: Ok, if you could just type that in.
15 S: Oh, so like, so is also with int...?
16 [END TASK 34A]
17 [00:03:00]
18 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34A]
19 R: Oh no, you just put the name in, that's fine. Ok. If you now look at the program code, so the algorithm that you see
here what you just described to me, how complex do you find that? On a scale from 0 to 10 and 0 means easy, 10 means very
complex.
20 S: So you need to know about the enhanced for-loop so it is like, it's not like something which you immediately know when
you have like, basic knowledge. Ehm, you know, you have to know that an array starts with zero, but I think in total it
would be a 4, I think.
21 R: Ehm, yeah. I'll tell you, because I have two questions, the second one is about the concepts. So the things that you
have mentioned, you have an array and you have to know that it has an index that starts with zero, that's actually the
conceptual-
22 S: So the first one would be-
23 R: The first one is more the algorithm, so how do you, what are the steps in it, like, here you have the-
24 S: I, I think the algorithm is doable, yeah.
25
26 [00:04:00]
27
28 R: Ok, and then the next one with the concepts?
29 S: Yeah, there I would say it was much more because for-loop and something that this is not what you'd learn on the first
page of Java: how to program book.
30 R: Which loop do you start with?
31 S: Ehm...
32 R: which loop, the while or the normal for, or...
33 S: Ehm, I think we... I started with the if-else statement and then there comes, I think, the while, then the normal for
and I think the enhanced for only saw this year, ehm, this semester in Java. So the answer, we've never had an enhanced for-
loop in C++.
34
35 [00:04:37]
36
37 R: Ok. Ehm, and how about the instructions, did you know what I wanted you to do?
38 S: No, I think they were quite clear. Only maybe before we begin, but in total...
39 [END DISCUSS TASK 34A]
40 [00:04:59]
41 [BEGIN TASK 34B]
42 R: Ok. So now I have another one that looks very similar, if you would look at the screen.
43 S: Yeah, again an array. Also int values, which are, yeah, same than above, then you get the local variable "i=0". And
while i is smaller than the length of the array, ehm, yeah, so it goes also through the array but with the while-loop, and
if "rainvalue" of i, so of the position i, is bigger than the, the already, defined value of 25, then ehm, this gets ehm,
then current gets this, this element again, so, and here you have an "i++". So, it does the same than the above code, but
only with a while-loop and with a, oh I read about this in a "how to program Java" book, where you have a while-loop which
ehm, the for-loop is exactly the while-loop but with fixed parameters. Yeah.
44 R: So you're saying that the for is the same as the while?
45 S: Yeah, if you implement it directly, but there's only, I think, one possibility where a for-loop can, where a while-loop
can be same as the for-loop. I think when you want to break out earlier, I think then it is not possible for a while-loop.
But, yeah.
46
47 [00:06:39]
48
49 R: Ok. And ehm, let's have a look, what would you call the, what would you call the function?
50 S: Ehm... [types "find_min_while"]
51 [END TASK 34B]
52 [00:07:02]
53 [BEGIN DISCUSS 34B]
54
55 R: With the while. Yeah, ok. If you look at now the programme code?
56 S: It's more complex.
57 R: And what makes it more complex?
58 S: The while-statement because it's like a little bit unclear where it goes to, but, so, in the other one I had earlier
the, the understanding of the whole thing. But there you have more like shifting, putting it somewhere else...
59 R: And what's shifting, and what's putting it somewhere else?
60 S: Like, like, i is smaller than this, and this has to be bigger than this and then this gets this, so this putting this
there, comparing, putting it back...
61 R: Yeah. So it's more spaced over the...?
62 S: Yeah. So the complexity here of the algorithm... Yeah, that's a good question because the for is more specific, but the
while-loop is, it's, it's, [the pure code?] of the while-loop is easier than the for-loop, but it makes this code more
complex.
63 R: Ok. And yeah, and yeah what cost for you the most energy to read? This one or the one before?
64 S: This one.
65 R: Ok, so then this would be easier... That's kind of what the... yeah.
66 S: But also doable. When I see the threads we are now doing then...
67 R: [laughs] yeah.
68 S: I'm glad that I can manage this.
69
70 [00:08:24]

```

Track changes is off

You: S1: construct familiarity. FOREACH harder because learned later
Jan 7, 2024 11:01 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O1: misconception verbalized
Jan 7, 2024 11:02 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S6: WHILE harder to follow
Jan 7, 2024 11:05 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

71
72 R: Ok. And the concepts? So...
73 S: Ehm, yeah, the concept is easier.
74 R: And what makes this concept easier than the for each?
75 S: Yeah, the while-loop is, ehm, something where you can have, where you can normally more think about, what-what can, what makes more logic for a normal human, you know? That you have, like, something which repeats every time to something and so this is normally a very familiar concept for people to first understand. Instead of doing this hundred times, you can just do it until you're done.
76
77 [00:09:05]
78
79 R: Ok, perfect. And, ehm, the task, how clear was it what I asked, what I wanted you to do?
80 S: Ehm...
81 R: So the question, was it clear when you read the question what you were supposed to do?
82 S: Oh, yeah, yeah.
83
84 [00:09:23]
85
86 R: Oh no, this is, sorry, that's clear, that's very unclear. So, yeah. Ok, perfect. Great. And... A last code-reading question.
87 [END DISCUSS TASK 34C]
88 [BEGIN TASK 34C]
89 S: Ehm... Yeah, again the int, ehm, int thing, array... Ehm, this time a local variable for... for the, ehm, for the int "i=0", so you also go through the array but with the normal for-loop there, and if the, the value you are looking at this moment is equal to zero, then you say the count is ++. So I think it's a, it's a, yeah it's a fun-it's a method, or function that ehm, finds the number of, the amount of all zeroes in an array. Like, the number of [low cues?].
90
91 [00:10:26]
92
93 R: Yeah. Great, okay. How would you call this?
94 S: [types "count_zero"]
95 [END TASK 34C]
96 [00:10:35]
97 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34C]
98 R: Ok. Now, if you look at the program code that you see here, how difficult, how complex is it?
99 S: That was quite doable. It was quite doable, yeah. So it was not complex. Well, it was fast through it.
100 R: Allright.
101 S: Ehm...
102 R: Ok, you're doubting because...?
103 S: Yeah, because just like, ehm... is it so easy or is it not so easy?
104 R: Ok, and the concepts, because now you say the, oh this is the normal for-loop?
105 S: Ehm... I think it... I think it makes sense, you don't have to think about complex. It's like, ehm, you're reading something mathematically, and you don't have to have a knowledge behind that, so you see like ok, is this about more than enhanced for-loops. So it's like an i, zero, so you can go step by step through the for-loop, which makes it easier for you to understand than enhanced for-loops. I think. So it is also not so complex. Because when you know the basics like, how a variable gets declared, what i++ is, then you can also understand the for-loop without knowing what a for-loop do.
106 S: Yeah, the instructions are like the same, also. Clear.
107 R: Yeah. Would you say the same, you say the for-loop you can use without having to know exactly what, how it works? would you say the same for the "println"? Because it is a function call and I know-
108 S: Ehm, if I'm honest, I still don't understand systems that output lines till now.
109 R: But you know what it does, right?
110 S: I know what it does, but-
111 R: What is, what, why, what does line 11 do?
112 S: Ehm, it prints a whole line, which ehm, ehm, I don't, it prints a line of the code, so the variable, like, which you have in the end, the amount of zeroes, is a number, and this number gets printed in one line.
113 R: Yeah. And how it works, we don't care. We know, you memorized it into print so whenever you need to print something you use it.
114 S: Yeah. So I think we start with learning that, ehm, there's systems that output line, and I think we never mentioned like, ok, from system there's a method out and there's the method print line, or how it works and what system for is a class kind of, so it's like, this is like, C out, and C++.
115 [END DISCUSS TASK 34C]
116 [00:13:39]
117 [BEGIN DISCUSS THREE READ TASKS]
118 R: Ok. Ehm, here I have the three pieces of code. This was the enhanced for-loop, this was the one with the normal for-loop and this is the while. Can I ask you to put it in order from most difficult to least, or most complex to least complex?
119 S: No, from the complexity or understanding?
120 R: Complexity.
121 S: I think this is definitely up, because it's the most complex, if you see immediately on all three codes, this is what takes the longest time to understand. Ehm, I think the for-loop, the enhanced for-loop then, and then I think this one.
122
123 [00:14:25]
124
125 R: Ok, yeah. Then we can add some things later. Ok, and you already explained it a little bit why. Perfect.
126
127 [END DISCUSS THREE READ TASKS]
128 R: Ok, now I'm going to ask you to write a little bit of code. Ehm, ehm, there's a run button but I'm gonna ask you not to use it. I don't care about syntax, that's not what I'm interested in, I'm interested in knowing what you're thinking about and what you're going through. So it's more about the algorithm, and I'd like you to focus on that, don't worry about the syntax. Ok? And if I let you run it, then you get feedback and through this research you're gonna learn, and-
129 S: Yeah, normally, ehm, the most where I learn is try-error, so...
130 R: Yeah [laughs]
131 [BEGIN TASK 81]
132 [00:15:01]
133 S: Ehm... [reads text] [silence for 17 seconds] How many days the maximum amount of rain fell? So I will say like, as simple as the code with the amount of zeroes, but then say like, you compare it in every step, so I will start like with a local variable, which is my counter, "int count" equals to zero. Oh, this keyboard...
134 R: Oh, yeah. We had another student here last week... Very annoying for me too.
135 S: Ehm... So you have a counter which is at the zero, so in the beginning you don't have any maximum wettest days. That makes sense. And then you have a for-loop, I will say, for ehm, like, all values in, I think it's the loophole, in "rainValues", so in the array. You, you have, ehm, you have rainValues of, I'm thinking about how you recognize the ++, you know, that you just say like, ok, compare with the next one or with the, or compare... So I think you need then in the beginning a local variable, which is set to also zero, which is zero "int max". Also is a zero. So say like, I will compare this everytime with max, and if max is smaller, then... then ehm, this value in this array gets the new max. So, if- statement... Max... Smaller than... smaller than rainValues... I think this is value... no... ehm... enhanced for-loops... I think this is doable. Oh... I feel so embarrassed. Ehm, then, ehm, ehm... then max equals to, or gets, gets the value of, of rainValues. Of values... And in the end, like, you have the remainders, again, again it gets everytime bigger and then you have in the end the biggest one. Ehm... [silence for 10 seconds]
136 R: What are you thinking about?
137 S: I'm thinking about, ehm, that you have to count the amount of max numbers. And you're now going through the array and find the maximum value but you don't know how often it occurs. And I can't say, like, after this under the if-statement, or can I? Like under the if-statement saying, if the maximum is smaller than this, making max equals, and if this is not the case, oh this is also not correct... Like, like, then saying counter++ but this also makes no sense. So you have a counter zero, and a max zero [refers to initialization]. And you're looking for array [mumbles] [silence for 10 seconds] Another if... [silence for 30 seconds] If max equals to rainvalue [types max = rainValues[values]], value, then ehm... set the... so there's a possibility, three possibilities, if it is bigger then ignore it, it is the biggest out of the for [loop], if

You: S5: WHILE intuitive

Jan 7, 2024 11:08 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

You: S3: FOREACH magical (harder to trace/understand)

Jan 6, 2024 3:06 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

You: S2: FOR understandable

Jan 6, 2024 3:01 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

You: O4: recognizes familiar plan

Jan 7, 2024 1:42 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

You: O1: misconception (verbalized): incorrect algorithm: should be larger than i.o. smaller than for max

Jan 7, 2024 1:44 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

You: O8: switches construct midway. Started with for-loop, now choose enhanced for loop

Jan 7, 2024 1:45 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve

Reply

You: O7: patchwork process. trying to add if-statements on the fly to make it work

Jan 7, 2024 1:48 PM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

it is smaller than the maximum is this rainvalue, and it is equal the max value should also get this rainvalue, but also the counter should get ++. So like, the max value equals to or gets, oh no, equal [fixes = to =]... Max when the value, of values, this happens and ehm, the counter we have set for gets increased. And in the end, after the for-loop you say ehm, like, system.out.println, out. Yeah.

138
139 [END TASK 81]
140 [00:23:03]
141
142 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 81]
143 R: Ok. Now, I have a question. Why did you use the for each?
144 S: Ehm, so the enhanced for-loop.
145 R: Sorry, yeah, the enhanced for-loop.
146 S: Because I heard that it [foreach] reduces the complexity and makes it better for efficiency.
147 R: Ok, no because you, it surprised me because in your ordering you said that it was difficult and you've had the least experience with it, so I was surprised to see that you chose.
148 S: Yeah, as you can see, it was not a good choice.
149 R: [laughs] No, what's wrong with the choice? Would it have been easier if you had done something else?
150 S: I think I, I think it was doable in the beginning, and when you type it down, then there comes more necessities and more things that have to be, and in total you write a code and not like you're starting with, ok, this, this, and end something, you start, you recognize there have to be something different or more, or better, or other, so in the end you're not writing the code down, you just try to fix your own problems, as you can saw after the if there was like, ok, I have some trouble, so how can I fix this, such that gives me in the end the result I needed?
151 R: Yeah, and would that have been different if you would have used a, the other, the normal for which you're more comfortable with? Would you've had less trouble? Because couldn't, could you have done this with a normal, with a regular for-loop?
152 S: I-I-I-I think the regular for-loop would be, there was one thing where I, ehm, struggled with, because the enhanced for-loop doesn't work for, ehm, if you want to change the elements in the array. So I was thinking about this, this at one point necessary, because otherwise I have to use the other for-loop. And I think sometimes this, this is my starting value, this is the length, or this is my end value and this is how it increases, helps me by finding a solution better. Here you have to think about ok, for, enhanced for-loop makes step by step and then you can see it so you can look up like ah, i++, so for next next there you have to think a little more complex and deeper.
153 R: Ok. Ok, thank you.
154 S: This doesn't work, right?
155
156 [00:25:46]
157
158 R: Ehm... So. [laughs] Oh, no you're really close but there's a few little things, so, but that's ok, that's ok. Ehm, the program code that you wrote, how complex do you find what you, if you look at it? The code that...
159 S: I think it was very complex because in the end it, I-I-I, in the beginning I thought it would be less complex, but after I have to fix my problems, it gets like a little bit chaotic, and I think this is a moment where you say like, ok I banish everything and maybe start over again thinking about the, the task before typing.
160
161 [00:26:26]
162
163 R: Ok. But if you like, look at the structure of the code that you used, you have a for-loop with an if and another if inside, ehm, what makes this complex?
164 S: The two if-statements because they're, there it switches between like, if this happens, this happens and for every one of these, or, yeah, the if-else, so you don't know exactly where the pipe goes.
165
166 [00:26:50]
167
168 R: Ok, and how about the concepts that you have?
169 S: I think the concepts are like, except the for-loop, it is not difficult, so, I would say a 2 or, yeah a 2.
170
171 [00:27:09]
172
173 R: Ok. And how clear were the instructions?
174 S: No, no, the instructions was clear. The one for, because the system is a bit, or the ehm, there you have to think about what you're reading.
175 R: Ok. Can you put this in your hierarchy somewhere? Tell me how difficult, on the top you had like the most complex, so this is the question you just did.
176 S: Yeah. I have to...?
177 R: Put it there in your...
178 S: Oh, where the, the complexity. Ehm...
179 R: You have the most complex on top, so...
180 S: Because there was one which counts the amount of zeroes, and this one, ehm, goes through the array and find the maximum, and I think because this is exactly these both, but combined in one, I think this is more difficult than this.
181 R: Ok. And you're making it your, you're putting it under the, ehm, the while-loop? Which went through the array one time. Is that on purpose?
182 S: Ehm, I don't know... Nah, I... Nah-ah, nah-ah, because if the while-loop is like, is also like, it's a bit more complex, but it's also only one task and not combining. But as I saw what I did, was getting closer to this than to the enhanced for-loop here.
183
184 [END DISCUSS TASK 81]
185 [00:28:49]
186 [BEGIN TASK 83b]
187 [00:28:55]
188 R: Yeah, ok. Thank you. I have another code-writing question for you.
189 S: [reads text] Index of the first rainy day... Ehm... [silence for 10 seconds] Ok. So, if there are no rainy days with an error message [I start loop?] and I said like, I go through the array and if there are only zeroes, so if there is nothing, not i, eh, if there's one that's not equal to zero, there's one which is equal... oh... yeah, if there is one which is not equal to zero, to the, the, the first rain and last rain task but if there is something, but if this is not the case... it's everytime this loop thing... so you wanna go through the array. The first to the last. And everyone, it should check a value, if it is zero or not. If it is zero, then you should count it, and if the length of the array is equal to this count, then the boolean value gets to the, decides about the error message. So, I forgot how to type booleans... boolean... sunny day... equals to false... Yeah... And you have again an "int count", that is counting the sunny days. This is also in the beginning zero. Then you have given the length of the array but you don't have to declare it. And you have, ehm, ehm... in, two indexes, so "indexfirst" equals to zero, and "indexlast" also equals to zero. Oh, I totally don't get it. I get, I get what they want, but I'm very bad at programming.
190 R: Oh, that doesn't matter.
191 S: Ok. Ehm, yeah then you start with, now is, now I get the normal for-loop. For... int i equals to zero... i smaller than the length of the array... [silence for 15 seconds] what is this size...
192 R: That doesn't matter.
193 S: Ok... i++... Then we decide if, what cases are possible, it is zero, or it is not zero. If it is not zero, then it's a rainy day. If it is zero... [silence for 12 seconds] If the value of... is zero... oh, value of i, equals to zero, of zero, of zero was easier. Not zero, or zero means it is a sunny day... So it just set the counts of ++. Because I want to compare the counts in the end with the length and if this is equal then I know that there are only sunny days. So, ehm, yeah then counts ++, and else, so then it is not sun, and it is not sunny, then there have to be also a question if this is the first or the last. [silence for 8 seconds] So for the first I will say if also local variables counts the, the rainy days where you say like, ok, if this is zero, then you say like, so when the count value is not zero, and the counter "int count_rain" is zero, and if this is the case, eh, so, else if, possibilities of just together, else if the count of rain equals to zero, then, we know it's the first day where it's rainy. So, this value of, ehm, this gets the index or the i, eh, indexfirst, then gets i. Because you want to have the index and not the value. Yeah. Ehm... so you start with if it is zero, count... mmm-hmm [mumbles]... now's the, now we solve the problem with the last one. Yeah there should be a code, something like, if the count is, you have to see the future, that's the problem. You have to see the array future that say like if there comes no zeroes anymore, ehm, ah also ehm, we say like index last, so if if or we have if this is

Resolve Reply

You: O1: verbalized misconception
Jan 6, 2024 4:46 PM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: O7: Patchwork process
Jan 7, 2024 1:50 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O7: patchwork process
Jan 7, 2024 1:53 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O5: lacking appropriate design prior to implementation
Jan 7, 2024 1:54 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S15: conditionals increase difficulty
Jan 7, 2024 1:55 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O4: recalls/recognizes learned plan
Jan 7, 2024 2:02 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S24: 2 subsequent plans harder than 1
Jan 7, 2024 2:26 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

187: if there comes no zeroes anymore, ehm... oh, okay. ehm... we say first, index last, so if it, if we have it, this is zero. Then you have a sunny day. So the counter gets ++. So in the end, after the for-loop we already can say if count equals to "rainValues.length"... then, I don't know if you want to have an exception...

194 R: No just print and say it's not raining or something.
195 S: System.out.println... [mumbles] Ehm...
196 R: No rain, that's fine.
197 S: Yeah, no, but then we have no rain... and if this is not the case, then we have rainy days, so, ehm, prints system.out... Ehm... println... first rainy, how do you say rainy... day... other point plus indexfirst... and the same... [silence for 15 seconds] for last. And I think I have a solution for my problem with the index last, because I can say like, we updated everytime that index last is the current index, if there is no, ehm, if it is, so index of last, so if it is zero, and if it is not zero, and it is not... so if the value itself is not zero, and the, the counter is not zero, then you know there is already a rainy day before that and it is a rainy day, so you say, this gets your indexlast. So indexlast equals, so else, ehm... indexlast gets i, so everytime when this happens again, it gets updated. And if there is zero, then the counter gets ++, but not the else-statement. So it's only a, everytime, or it goes through the loop, and first decides if it is rainy or not, and if it is sunny, it implements the counter, which in the end gets compared, and if not then it decides if it is the first rainy day, or if it is not the first rainy day, you just say ok, this, this rainy day today will get the last one, and I do this as long as there is a rainy day in the array. And if there's no one, this not get updated, so the last index is then, so that would be my problem.

198
199 [00:41:50]
200
201 R: Ok. All right, then I'm gonna ask you what...
202 S: Yeah, yeah. I have, I never used the boolean so I can delete the boolean because I found out this, no, not found out but...
203
204 [END TASK 83b]
205 [00:42:05]
206 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 83B]
207
208 R: Figured out later it was... yeah. Ok. Then, I'd like you to have a look at the code that you wrote. How complex is the...?
209 S: This time it was quite easier. Ehm, for myself, for my brain.
210 R: For your brain? [laughs] Yeah, what made it easier?
211 S: Because when I normally do this, I have paper and make like, ok, if this happens, if this happens, such that I never make because I have also ADHD and with ADHD it's a problem to structure things. So for me it is, if-else-statement is for me very complex. That's not so for everyone, so everybody looks like, ok, if else-if, so I'm there, but I don't know if it can happen that also when this happens, you're landing in there.

212
213 [00:42:53]
214
215 R: And do you find and if-else more complex than a for-loop? An iteration that happens the whole time?
216 S: Yeah. It's a switch, that if-else not, but if-elseif [elseif], so if it gets, if you not have the switch, if you have the switch of a switch, then it gets for myself, like, we had once the task of computing the, this year, if this is a leap year, and there was like, if it is divisible by a hundred, but not divisible by four hundred and this, and I really don't get it. It tooks me two hours to find it out, and it was only this kind of code, so.

217 R: Yeah, complex conditions. Ok.
218 S: So this was not so complex, or it is good readable, I think.
219
220 [00:43:45]
221
222 R: All right. And the concepts that you used then?
223 S: They were also in itself, only the, the if-elseif statement.
224 R: And do you mean, this the if, the else-ifelse, or do you only mean the else-if? What part specifically?
225 S: I think only the elseif. or the combining between elseif and the else in the end because I never know the jumping, where it jumps then.

226
227 [00:44:16]
228
229 R: Yeah, ok. And did you know what you had to do?
230 S: Ehm... There was one thing where I thought about... can I go... I thought about [reads text] ehm... [silence for 12 seconds] No, it was good.
231 R: What would you score...
232 S: Oh, maybe like what kind of error message, because there are some things like exception or just an error message print out, or what, or just like we did it, just the information but not an error, so maybe two. But the, but the example was quite helpful. But I wanted, I wish to have, it's also in the exam so would wish to have an example for every case.
233 R: Yeah, okay, yeah yeah yeah.
234 S: And the whole structure, what he wants from you, so for example that there was also, there would be also an example of what happens when they're all zero.

235
236 [00:45:34]
237
238 R: Yeah, when they're all zero. Ok, thank you. Ehm, I'd like to do one more. Is that ok?
239 S: I think I have to be there at three after three, so...
240 R: Yeah, you'll be done with this one by then. [laughs] Hold on, before you start, would you put this in the order? This is the one we just did, the rainy day, last rainy day, and we had the most difficult, most complex there on top.
241 S: It was quite more difficult than the normal ones, all the single things, because it was also combinations, but this time I don't, I can't tell you why it was easier for me than the first one.
242 R: Ok, perfect. Ok, all right.
243 [END DISCUSS TASK 83B]
244
245 [BEGIN TASK 90]
246 [00:46:26]
247 S: [reads text] we had this in the solving algorithms. Yeah, we have to count things, and there was like, the... Weather station keeps track of rainfall... Ok, same than normal. [reads text] So a millimeter of rain is here one number, I think, so if there's three, this means three mm, so it'd have to be three asterisks, as you can see in the example. Ehm... okay, yeah. [reads text] Ok. So what you have to do is, you go again through the array and for every element you have to find out the value, and this value have to decide, ehm, how often this loops, this loop, ehm.. how do you say it... how often it will execute the...
248 R: Oh, sorry.
249 S: Ehm...
250 R: So you said, for [?] the value and for every value...
251 S: So what kind of, ehm... local variables do you need, you need... So you need two loops. One goes through the array and one decides for every array how often you print the... Can I use the paper?
252 R: Oh sure.
253 S: Small one's enough. So, ehm... The middle part's like system... So the smallest thing you do is system.out.println, one [asterisk?]. So, and you decide how often this happens, println, or no. It's print, and after, a number, the number of the first array, element decides how often this happens. So the three, so rainValues of i... it's equal or you have a for-loop, oh this is smaller... You have a for-loop, this is int, i equals to zero, and this terminates after i is smaller, equal than rainValues of i... of i... i++. And then you say, system.out.println, and after this you say ok, this is the end of the for-loop, so you do it for every value, and after that you say ok, system.out.println, or println like nothing. Or like, how do you call it... How do you print the...
254 R: Just close the bracket and you're done.
255 S: Like, nothing... So and, around this, because this is one element and one horizontal line. You want to have for every horizontal line, so you make again a for-loop with int, I think j, let's say j, zero. And j is smaller than the length of the rainValue array. Ehm... .length... and ehm, yeah, j++, ehm, I think you don't need to prepare something. No, so you go in with the first element. then you sav for every. from zero to the value of this element... Then you make after you have

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Resolve Reply

You: S16: selections with multiple branches difficult

Jan 7, 2024 2:19 PM • Edit

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Resolve Reply

You: S21: unconfident reasoning about control flow

Jan 7, 2024 2:30 PM • Edit

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Resolve Reply

You: O10: recalls familiar plan (So O10 should be 0)

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You: S21: unconfident reasoning about control flow

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You: O10: recalls familiar plan (So O10 should be 0)

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Resolve Reply

You: O11 coding error but OK in interview

Jan 11, 2024 5:12 PM • Edit

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reached the value... system.out a new line, and then you should start with the next... Yeah I think this should...

256

257 [END TASK 90]

258 [00:51:41]

259 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 90]

260 R: Ok, perfect. I'm not gonna ask you to type it in, you don't have to. I might as well, I'm just gonna, put one thing down, just the order in which you wrote things down, because I found that very interesting. Oh, did you do the for, yeah and you did this, crossed that one out and you did that and you did that. I find it very interesting, the way you work inside out.

261 S: Yeah, I thought like, you have a Java [?], and it have to be, when you have more than one for-loop, it is mostly, or like we learned it in imperative programming where we made the four weeks of just recursion. Sometimes it's smarter to see the base cases and then making loops around it such that it is, that the, because it's then everytime only one base case, but it depends on, ehm, the outcome depends on the structure flow. So this is the reason why I started in the middle.

262 R: But you knew that you needed, because you told me in the beginning you need two for-loops, and you know that this isn't nested inside that, right? And did you, you knew that right away? Did you know when you started it would be a for-loop inside a for?

263 S: Yeah, because we had two [legend?] arrays. And there was much often like, work in column. And much often, and I thought like, ok, you have a task, and this gets for every element done. So you have some units goes as I said in the end you start with one and in this one you do something. And so, yeah. So I think nested for-loops are quite easier than with data flow. So this task would be the easiest one.

264

265 [00:53:34]

266

267 R: Ok. Well, let me give you the, what's this one?

268 S: This one [reads text] Yeah, and I would, yeah, as I said, put it there. Because we really often did these nested problems. And it is quite useful to make a chart up in the game, we had earlier the game of life where this asterisks would change and the two print out the both of that. You have like, nested for-loops which, yeah.

269

270 [00:54:08]

271

272 R: Ok, awesome. Ok. Now I'm gonna ask you to answer the survey. So if you look at the programme code you have here, how complex do you find it?

273 S: Oh, it's only a bit data flow I think, so it's a one, because it's only a little bit data flow. But the things are quite simple. And the task... [reads text] This was how complex the total thing is, huh?

274 R: Well, the concepts itself. The total things is this one. This is the fact that you have a for-loop.

275 S: Ok, well, I would say this [nested for] is a bit more than this [for each], but also not much because this is a nested for-loop. And this is a little bit like you have once go in your head through some variables, this is what I everytime do like, ok, I have a three, so I start there and go through the while-end. But the principles are just two fors and just simple and just some brackets, so.

276 R: So, a nested for-loop is not much more difficult than two fors after each other? Because the fact that how you ordered it, let's see, you put it under, we needed to find the, the top one. How many days the maximum amount of rain fell, you went through the list two times. First you had to find the maximum and then you had to count them. So you did a for, then afterwards a for and a while, and you did one loop and then when you were done you did another loop.

277 S: No, for me the nested for-loop is easier. Yeah. Also for my understanding that you have like, a table.

278

279 [00:56:00]

280

281 R: Yeah. Ok. All right, and how clear was it, your instructions, what was asked from you?

282 S: Yeah, it was quite clear.

283 R: Ok, perfect. Ok, awesome! All right, we're done. Thank you very much.

284

285 [END DISCUSS TASK 90]

286 [hands out gift]

287

288 [00:56:57]

289

You: S9: nested for loops is easy
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You: S9: nested loops easy
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You: S9: nested loops easy (plan -
table)
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